

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase

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D6.1 Standards & protocols for FAIR data management identification

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List of abbreviations

- AAAI: Authentication & Authorisation and Accounting Infrastructure
- API: Application Programming Interface
- CSA: Coordination and Support Action
- DoA: Description of Action
- DOI: Digital Object Identifiers
- DMP: Data Management Plan
- DXWG: Data Exchange Working Group
- EC: European Commission
- EML: Ecological Metadata Language
- ENVRI: Environmental Research Infrastructure
- EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
- ESFRI: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure
- FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.
- GA: Grant Agreement
- IPR: Intellectual Property Rights
- ISO: International Organization for Standardization
- LL: Living Lab
- OAI-PMH: Open Archive Initiative - Protocol for Metadata
- ORD: Open Research Data Pilot
- PID: Persistent Identifiers
- RDA: Research Data Alliance
- RI: Research Infrastructure
- RDF: Resource Description Framework
- SDO: Standards Developing Organisations
- URI: Uniform Resource Identifier
- URL: Uniform Resource Locator
- XML: Extensible Markup Language
- W3C: World Wide Web Consortium
- WP: Work package

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Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LLs) and Research Infrastructures (RIs) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

This deliverable *D6.1 Standards & protocols for FAIR data management identification* develops the results of *T6.2 Guaranteeing Open Data FAIRness*. This task set the basis to enhancing the harmonisation of ALL-Ready data FAIRness and reinforcing the functional collaboration among the network stakeholders, capitalising on agroecology specificities and strength points by implementing the FAIR principles into the data life cycle of the network.

Deliverable D6.1 presents a research work to identify the most suitable standards and protocols for a FAIR data management. This includes data formats, enriched metadata management, and quality control procedures. The standards and protocols will be considered in order to guarantee FAIRness on interoperability and reusability applied to agroecology (meta-)data of relevance.

This document states the basis and principles for the FAIR data management that will be performed during the project. The information collected during this research is used for the establishment of the Data Management Plan (D6.2), but also for the co-design and co-development of the Virtual Research Environment (integrating Blockchain-based technology) and other e-Services led by LifeWatch ERIC in WP6.

1. About Data Management in Research

Data management refers to the organisation, storage, preservation, and sharing of data collected and used in a research project [1]. An increase in the connectivity has accelerated the accessibility to scientific research activity and results. A recent study stated that the scientific output is doubling approximately every ten years [2]. This fact makes essential to generate a proper data management for the entire data lifecycle. This means that a detailed planning and procedures are needed for all the stages of data throughout its life from its creation for a research study to its distribution and reuse. This plan should be prepared in advance, even during the development of the concept for a study, so that the collection and preservation of the data gathered during this study can be ensured. If this is not the case, data generated from research is at risk of being lost forever [3]. In fact, it has been demonstrated that the availability of data related to research projects declines speedily with the age of a study. The probability of datasets being considered as available can decrease 17% each year after publication [4]. Apart from that, more and more institutions such as universities and research funding agencies but also academic journals are requesting data management plans and data sharing. For instance, the European Commission encourages the submission of a Data Management Plan (DMP) for the projects of the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and this is compulsory when the projects participate in the Open Research Data (ORD) pilot [5]. The ORD pilot aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects and takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions [5]. Therefore, there is a strong need for focused attention on the stewardship of research data.

Several reasons make research data management essential for the entire data lifetime apart from the fragility and the high risk of data loss and the impositions made by funders and publishers. Data management saves time and resources in the long run, and eases the everyday data handling, but also facilitates decisions about how data will be preserved and shared after the project is completed. Data management also minimises errors and increases the quality of analyses [1]. An important point is that research data management facilitates sharing of research data and, when shared, data can lead to valuable discovery by external collaborations with others outside of the original research team. The research data is meticulously collected, analysed, optimised, organised, and made usable to carry out research studies. Data sharing is increasingly encouraged and occasionally mandated by publishers and research institutions and the benefits are manifold (Table 1, [6]):

Table 1 Benefits from data sharing (From Patel, 2016 [6])

Benefits	Explanation
Improve reusability	Data can be reused by other researchers and applied in various other contexts.
Increase research citation	The data collectors and analysts also get credit and acknowledgement through data citation.
Gain trust	The authenticity and objectivity of the data will be reaffirmed by usage. Data citation will also increase the trust in the data set as source and attribution becomes clear.
Increase transparency	Data sharing brings transparency in the research process and data collection methods.
Improve timesaving	It saves a lot of time for the researchers, so they can focus on newer avenues of research instead of collecting data from scratch.

A deep understanding of data management should be put into practice in the early stage of a research project. The issues related to research data management are varied and complex and may require technical and legal expertise. Therefore, it is imperative that institutions, universities and research infrastructures put in place their knowledge and mechanisms to manage research data sets.

2. About Data Management Plans

Before a new project or experiment starts, it is essential to define the best approach to manage the different steps in the data life cycle. This previous definition leads to great advantages such as reduced time and effort but also investment [1]. During this **planning stage**, researchers should identify data sources that will be used during the project, data and metadata formats that will be managed, instrumentation and computing resources that will be required, among other important topics (ethic and security issues, specific authorisations, specialised human resources needed, etc.). By doing this, data providers are increasing the project efficiency because they avoid problems that otherwise will surely appear during the project implementation [7]. However, and despite its importance, the planning stage in the Data Life Cycle is one of the least adopted by the community. The reason is that data providers (such as researchers) usually see this as a bureaucratic or administrative task to waste time. However, they should consider that this is the right moment to carefully think about what is going to be done, how and why and following what possible methodology will produce best results. A **good data management planning** should consider the basic administration details to be thought along with the data life cycle, mainly: 1) the type of data collected, 2) formats, 3) how data will be collected, 4) resources needed, 5) different roles in data life cycle [1]. Furthermore, planning should also consider how data could be exploited after the project ends, or how they can be reused in other projects. It means that a wider vision exceeding the scope of the project is needed, and in

this phase, data providers should give details on how data will be published, using adequate formats and metadata standards. Planning should be understood like an opportunity to organise the data and optimise the use of resources [7].

The importance of the planning phase in data life cycle has been **reinforced by funding bodies worldwide**. The investment that the governments make funding projects and the increasing importance of the data itself generated by the community has triggered further efforts for promoting data management practices, especially in the research context. Therefore in 2013, during the G8 science ministers meeting, it was discussed and agreed internationally that “Publicly funded scientific research data should be open” [8] as well as “Open scientific research data should be easily discoverable, accessible, assessable, intelligible, usable, and wherever possible interoperable to specific standards”. These policy decisions have promoted the establishment of mechanisms to ensure that projects results should revert into the society in the form of open data, but also a new element in research projects such as the Data Management Plan (DMP).

It is not clear, especially for researchers, the importance that **Data Management Plans** have. DMPs facilitate data reusing because they contain a coherent set of sections describing how data life cycle is handled. Therefore, data can be tracked along its life, including mechanisms to ensure the provenance traceability. Moreover, DMPs ensure reproducibility because they describe all the elements related to the data gathering, curation, and analysis, so the results of the research can be reproduced in the future. DMPs also reduce control costs as a consequence of the provision of a way to estimate and limit the costs associated with data collection. DMPs must include a clear description of the purpose of the data gathering, including what is needed for the research project and the expected results or findings. The planning provided by DMPs provides a roadmap for the data lifecycle. The preparation of a DMP is the phase where all the elements that may influence the data life cycle can be integrated from a global perspective. This way, the resources can be optimised, and no-sense or duplicated actions avoided. DMPs allow the capture of requirements along all the data life cycle phases. Although DMPs are sometimes considered as a static document, ideally it can be progressively updated taking into account the evolution along the data life cycle. DMPs should not be “closed” before the project starts, as unexpected issues will appear, nor “started” by the end of the project, when data may even have already disappeared. Despite the importance of Data Management Plans, an ideal formula to be agreed by both funders and researchers has not yet been found. However, in recent years, lots of effort were put into enabling automated and machine-actionable mechanisms, supported by services in the cloud, to improve this essential phase in research [7].

DMPs are a key element of good data management. They are defined as “a formal document that outlines how you will handle your data both during your research, and after the project is completed” [9]. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated. These documents are required for all the Horizon 2020 projects that participate in the ORD pilot. Moreover, all projects are still encouraged to submit a DMP on a voluntary basis. As part of making research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR, see Section 3), a DMP should include information on [5]:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project,
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated,
- which methodology and standards will be applied,
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

LifeWath ERIC is responsible for the preparation of the DMP for the ALL-Ready project. The DMP will contain information on the suggested policies, standards, and sustainability

activities related to the created data services, including software solutions for the services. This will be done in close collaboration with the rest of the work packages, focusing on FAIR policies (see Section 3) and common technical solutions, to ensure the management of knowledge in the project which is maintained following the FAIR principles. The DMP covers the data, documents and solutions created within the project, as well as policies and DMP recommendations to Living Labs, Open Innovation Arrangements, their connexion with Research Infrastructures and the inter-operability of the data produced. It describes the data (including metadata) and software standards, availability, curation and preservation methods, and is based on the Digital Curation model for DMPs, based on LifeWatch ERIC experience integrated within ENVRIplus¹ and ENVRI-FAIR² (ESFRI ENVIRONMENT Cluster) DMPs development experience (Digital Curation Centre) and synergies with other pan-European Research Infrastructures [10]. The ENVRIplus Research Infrastructures, where LifeWatch ERIC is an active member, have developed DMPs, tools and guidelines and utilise these as a basis for internal policymaking, road mapping, technological planning and governance of asset management, the latter within the framework of governance established by the Research Infrastructures e.g., the governance of a consortium through a consortium agreement. They are also used in the context of external agreements on transnational access [11]. These recommendations have been followed for the elaboration of this deliverable, but also for the DMP of the project.

3. About FAIR principles

The term FAIR refers to a set of guiding principles to make data **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**. FAIR principles were developed in 2014 and published two years later [12]. They consist of a list with 15 principles, and then, a set of 14 metrics have been defined to quantify levels of FAIRness [12]. The latest developments on FAIR are available at GO-FAIR³. In general terms, research data should be FAIR. These principles precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific technology, standard, or implementation solution [5].

The FAIR principles are characterised as:

Findable

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.
- F2. data are described with rich metadata.
- F3. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
- F4. metadata specify the data identifier.

Accessible

- A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol.

¹ <https://www.envriplus.eu/>

² <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/>

³ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

- A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
- A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary.
- A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

Interoperable

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Re-usable

- R1. meta(data) have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
 - R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
 - R1.2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance.
 - R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

Although good data management is not a goal in itself, it is a necessary condition that enables innovation, knowledge creation, data and knowledge integration, and reuse of data by other users. There are currently many factors missing or inadequately implemented, and also many institutional barriers that limit the deployment of research data. This situation can be improved using a systematic approach in applying these principles in order to maximise the FAIRness of data management.

Specific DMP requirements vary among the different funders. For the context of this deliverable, it is interesting to analyse the different requirements that the European Commission (EC) includes in its H2020 programme [5], and it is directly related to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The main requirements are the following (Table 2):

Table 2 Data Management Plan requirements

Requirement	Explanation
Context of the data	A DMP, according to the EC requirements, should include the status of the data in terms of type and/or origin, which means the way to get this data: reused from third parties, gathered by instrumentation, observations, etc. This context point must also explain the relation to the project objectives and justify why data is relevant. Other issues like the expected size of the data must be considered, as well as an outline of the data utility, specifying why the data could be useful and to whom.
To make the data findable	It must include a description of the metadata to be used, the element that describes the data itself. It must include the specification of the standard used, or at least a description of the metadata type to be used. Other aspects like the use of persistent identifiers and their type or the procedure for naming or versioning must be integrated. The idea is to prepare the data for publication and also to enable mechanisms for its discoverability. For example, the OAI-PMH protocol promotes the use of open APIs to exchange metadata information [7].
To make the data accessible	If data is not open for a good reason (ethical, privacy, security), it must be correctly justified. This point also includes details on how the data is to be accessed: the software that can be used, associated protocols, etc. It could also include embargo periods and their justification.
To make the data interoperable	In this sense, the use of metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies ensuring interoperability must be specified.
To make the data reusable	Licenses should be described, in terms of future data exploitation, potential restrictions and details about preservation

As the European Commission is not currently providing a specific service to complete the requested Data Management Plans, there are different ways to prepare it by following these suggestions, although the five points are mandatory. On the contrary, institutions like the National Science Foundation⁴ only require a two-page document in an almost free format. The following sections will provide more information about vocabularies, standards and protocols to cover the previous points about FAIRness.

4. Standards and protocols for FAIR data management

Becoming **fully FAIR compliant presents many challenges** for data providers and data. First of all, the way to define **the concept of FAIRness is continuously evolving** and has different interpretations depending on the community of practices. For instance, there is

⁴ <https://www.nsf.gov/>

considerable discussion in different communities such as the GoFAIR⁵ initiative and the Research Data Alliance (RDA⁶) [11].

One of the biggest challenges is that different groups usually rely on legacy databases and metadata systems that were built years ago (if they exist). They are based on highly specialised and often informal and dynamically generated community standards [11]. Under this scenario, the linking to external catalogues necessary to increase findability of the data is extremely difficult. An important and necessary first step for FAIRness is the development of controlled vocabularies and data type registries, that document and stabilise the community standards [11].

A **standard** is commonly defined as an agreed way of doing something. It determines the requirements and conditions for the description, interoperability, citation, sharing, publication, or preservation of all type of digital objects (e.g., data, code, algorithms, workflows, software, or papers). For data management, we will focus on standards for datasets and their associated contextual metadata (e.g., minimum reporting requirements, terminologies, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, thesauri, ontologies), or file formats or conceptual models. But there are also standards for analysis (e.g., standardised descriptions of the software used and workflow descriptions) and for code and algorithms that are employed, or software that has been developed (e.g., open version repositories and documentation).

The effort that are currently devoted to standards are focused on closing existing gaps (by the creation of *de novo* standards), harmonising efforts on similar standards or improving rules for existing standards [13].

Standards for the description, interoperability, citation, etc. are central to FAIR principles. Their Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reproducible status is ensured by groups facilitating their implementation, such as the FAIRsharing platform [14]. Standards harmonise data and metadata in regard to structure, format and annotation. As a consequence, their contents are open to transparent interpretation, reuse, integrative analysis and comparison. Because there are used by many stakeholders from all sectors, data and metadata standards are essential to roll out the FAIR principles. Official standards are designed by formal Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs) such as the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO). Collective endeavour also leads to the development of standards which are commonly accepted.

Throughout the data cycle (collection, annotation, preservation, publication, sharing and reuse), thousands of standards and databases are involved. Various challenges are faced by consumers and producers of such standards or data, such as the identification of the most relevant resources for domain and the production of findable data respectively [14].

⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

5. Application of standards and protocols for guaranteeing FAIRness on interoperability and reusability applied to agroecology

Open data, along with the **FAIR principles** are safeguarded by the European Open Science Framework. To comply with these principles, two phases in the data life cycle are key, Ingest and Preserve, because it is when data reach their mature stage and thus can be distributed to the community. Metadata, persistent identifiers and storage solutions are among the tools that uphold such principles [7].

It is essential to provide data with key information to describe their context and content before access is provided. This information guarantees data are **findable** and **accessible** to users without exhaustive search and can contribute to the automation of data discover and data processing. The Ingestion stage is supported by **metadata**, which provides information to understand datasets (coverage, units, provenance...). Exploiting metadata enormously contributes to address data FAIRness.

Another essential aspect of data FAIRness is **providing access** to the dataset. To do so, data should be unequivocally identified. This issue can be addressed by Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) by adding information on how to get access to the corresponding digital object. An interesting point of these identifiers is that they should return a description of the dataset and its context, although the dataset is temporally not accessible.

Data **preservation** should also be addressed to secure long-term exploitation, taking into consideration security and legal matters, authorisation for access, licensing policies, etc. The medium where data is stored also must be considered taking into consideration the expected usage. Finally cloud computing has a role to play in integrating these solutions [7].

5.1 METADATA

Metadata, defined as data about data, are essential elements that provide a description of data, their context, content and additional information [7]. The information they provide is important to understand the data before analysing the content itself. Their use should be well defined and described to be understood by humans and **accessible** by machines. Scientific and non-scientific projects are generating large amount of heterogenous data coming from different disciplines and sources that should be integrated [15]. Metadata can bring mechanisms to make them interoperable, based on harmonization processes. Furthermore, metadata help to support the four FAIR principles, by making data findable, accessible and reusable.

The most relevant objectives of Data Management Plans have been described in Section 2. Data Management Plans are essential for providing mechanisms that help to exploit data after the project. This future data exploitation needs to be supported by metadata which provide a description of data that can help to understand them. The proper definition of metadata adequate for the specific dataset should be reinforced by the community, academic institutions and funding bodies to support the FAIR principles [7].

For data to be interoperable and interpreted by humans and machines, metadata should be created under “discipline-oriented or generic standards”. In this regard, the Dublin Core [16] is the simplest metadata standard used by the scientific community. Indeed, it can be used to define any digital or physical objects. Dublin Core is well used by many researchers from different disciplines, and it has been widely used by other metadata standards for other disciplines. For instance, Darwin Core, based on Dublin Core standards have been used in biodiversity research.

A current challenge that researchers, academic institutions and funding bodies are facing is **making metadata useful and precise**. Some issues have been identified in the optimisation of the use of metadata such as compatibility among disciplines or metadata standards, preservation of datasets and metadata, limits to data sharing in terms of legal issues, and the level of human-dependency [7]. These limits are addressed by various groups like the Research Data Alliance (RDA⁷) that promotes best practices and technical solutions to build a sustainable system. RDA is working on the establishment of a basis for using metadata standards to ensure data interoperability promoting specific tools and methodologies. For instance, RDA has provided a Metadata Standards Directory to help data users to choose among different existing standards instead of starting from scratch with new or ad hoc solution for projects or experiments. This tool has been also reinforced by a Metadata Standards Catalogue that provides machine-actionable features. Although a regular use of metadata in scientific data is missing, the promotion of standards addressed to serve both humans and machines is essential to ensure FAIR principles are applied.

5.1.1 FAIR principles and metadata

The importance of metadata is well acknowledged. Metadata describe, provide information and relate research datasets with various other entities. However, we can also identify potential concerns respecting its status:

- Lack of metadata for a given dataset.
- Need of additional effort to deduce metadata from existing descriptive text or unstructured information. In this case, further efforts are needed to understand properly the dataset, and usually can lead to misinterpretation. Moreover, the requirement of human intervention makes the process unscalable.
- Use an unsuitable standard, leading to inconsistencies with the metadata used in other peer datasets.
- Many different standards for a specific area, which make difficult to share data and lead to a dilution of the community effort.

Metadata solution should always be included in DMP of project gathering data. It is needed to decide if an existing standard already exists or if it is necessary to develop a specific solution for the project. Another important aspect is that metadata needs to have a clear objective of FAIRness to support interoperability. Best practices and recommendations have been identified by a group of stakeholders (scholars, archivists, funders...) named FORCE11⁸ to facilitate knowledge discovery, accessibility, integration and analysis of data by humans and machines (automatic management of data). The effort of this group is valuable to

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁸ <https://www.force11.org/>

enhance the ability of machines to automatically manage the data alongside supporting the reuse by humans.

The four principles are related but they are independent and can be separately addressed. The implementation of them assists humans in getting a better understanding of the content of data resource by adding a context to data, in a persistent way. These principles also enable machine-actionability, the possibility that machines apply automatic mechanism for data processing and analysis without human interaction. The FAIR principles should be applied to additional elements of the data life cycle: tools, algorithms, workflows. Moreover, FORCE11 also promote the integration of such other digital objects. Such elements are of great importance in the implementation of the Reproducibility principle (not originally included in the FAIR principles). This new principle ensures that a dataset can be recreated. For achieving this goal, provenance, mechanisms and processes related to its creation, and the relationship among different components, should be identified and preserved. The application of this principle ensures transparency in research, reduces errors and, definitely, improves data quality [7]. For this project and when possible, provenance management will be strongly based on the service infrastructure of LifeBlock, the LifeWatch ERIC blockchain-based technology platform [10].

5.1.2 Metadata standards and interoperability between data catalogues

It has been said that the usefulness of metadata depends on whether they are understandable to people or applications that use them. Metadata is only useful if it is comprehensible to people or applications that use it [11, 17]. In order to facilitate the understanding, metadata usually follow standardised schemas (i.e., structures) based on recommendations from international organisations such as ISO (International Organization for Standardization). Usually, there are **various metadata standards** that can be used in the different disciplines, and specifically in environmental science and the agricultural domain. To simplify integration within systems metadata, a machine-readable language is often used such as XML or RDF or even JSON-LD [11]. A short description of them will be provided.

Standards can be defined as “the formal specification of the attributes (characteristics) employed for representing information resources” [18]. Specifically, the standards ISO 23081 on Metadata defines **metadata schema** as a “logical plan showing the relationships between metadata elements, normally through establishing rules for the use and management of metadata specifically as regards the semantics, the syntax and the optionality” [19]. A metadata schema could be understood as a as a group of elements with a detailed definition of its elements (i.e., semantic) and optionally rules on how and what values can be given to these elements. Generally, the terms ‘schema’ and ‘standard’ are used in a similar way. However, it is not exactly the same. When a metadata schema is developed and maintained by a standardisation body, then it is called **metadata standards** [20]. Below we provide a collection of some relevant standards to be considered during the project implementation [9]:

- **ISO 19115** [21] and **ISO 19139** [22] are international standards for geographic datasets. Both standards have been the base of **INSPIRE**⁹, an EU directive that aims to create a European Union spatial data infrastructure for the purposes of EU

⁹ <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>

environmental policies and policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment.

Specifically, ISO 19115 is an internationally adopted standard that provides a clear procedure for describing geographic datasets so that users can determine whether the data will be useful to them and how to access them. By establishing a common set of metadata terminology and definitions, this standard promotes the appropriate use and effective exchange of geographic information. This standard has other benefits, as it facilitates the organisation and maintenance of data and provides information about one organisation's dataset to others. This standard has been the base of

ISO 19139, in turn, is an international standard that provides clear metadata implementation standards for digital geographic datasets. The ISO 19139 standard was designed to provide a common specification for the description, validation and exchange of geographic datasets, which will promote interoperability and leverage the benefits of ISO 19115 into concrete implementation specifications. This document defines how metadata conforming to ISO 19115 should be stored in XML format. Both standards, ISO 19115 and ISO 19139 help to make data and metadata interoperable and should be taken into consideration during project implementation as a consequence of the geographical dimension of agroecological data.

- **DataCite** [23] is an international consortium founded in 2009 with an explicit emphasis on making research data citable, giving them a 'value' during the scientific process. In this way, this initiative should be taken into consideration because help to make data findable and reusable through the use of Persistent Identifiers for Digital Objects in order to unambiguously identify a digital resource, established as DOIs.
- **Dublin Core Metadata Schema** [24] is one of the simplest and most widely used metadata schema. This schema is provided by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative and originally it was conceived with the objective of achieving "consensus on a list of metadata elements that would yield simple descriptions of data in a wide range of subject areas for indexing and cataloguing on the Internet" [24]. Dublin Core includes 15 core metadata elements and has been represented progressively over time by text, HTML, XML and RDF. Only in this latter form does it approach the requirement for formal syntax and declared semantics. Nowadays, the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative is an organisation that provides support in metadata design and also provides best practices across the metadata domain.
- **CERIF** [25] is the Common European Research Information Format and is considered a data model recommended by the European Union to the Member States for research information.
- **DCAT** [26] is a World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) recommendation 'data catalogue vocabulary' and has the advantage of being conceived natively with qualified relationships and use of RDF (Resource Description Framework) triples. It is currently undergoing revision by the DXWG (Data Exchange Working Group).
- **Schema.org** is considered as a collaborative and community activity that has the mission to create, maintain and promote schemas for structured data on Internet and beyond. It is an initiative founded by Google, Microsoft, Yahoo and Yandex and now a community activity. It essentially provides a list of attributes, some with related vocabularies, for entities. It may be encoded in RDF or JSON-LD.

All previous standards and initiative have some relevance to ENVRI Community (Environmental Research Infrastructure Community) and therefore to ALL-Ready. Research Infrastructures (RI)s are encouraged to choose a schema that has the capability to describe their 'world of interest'. In this sense, in ALL-Ready, lessons learnt in ENVRI and EOSC previous projects and initiatives will provide the guarantee to deliver FAIR data management based on rich metadata schemas. However, it is essential to balance between generic to specific standards. While Dublin Core and DataCite are generic metadata standards with the objective of providing a minimum of metadata elements for describing a digital resource, other standards such as ISO19115 and ISO19139 [21,22] are specific for georeferenced data. The question of how to find an equilibrium between general information that is sufficient to search and access research data across scientific disciplines on the one side and specific information describing resources from certain research communities on the other side is not clearly answered yet. In this sense and with the aim of overcoming this problem, Research Data Alliance (RDA) is working on a set of common metadata elements, linked by qualified references, to act as rich metadata set for achieving FAIR principles in data management [12].

5.1.3 Cloud and metadata: machine-actionable metadata

Machine-actionable capacities are essential to automatise FAIR data management. The word "machine-actionable" is defined as the capacity of a dataset, tool, system or any other digital object to provide information about itself. This characteristic allows external agents such as algorithms, workflows or software to perform actions automatically on it. If it is correctly configured, the information provided should allow to automatically identify the type of the encountered object, decide if the content is or is not useful, check the license to certify if the object is accessible and can also perform an action like downloading, querying or analysing [7].

The machine-actionability of datasets and the associated metadata is needed if we want to automatise different procedures such as quality management, integrity tests, etc. Therefore, if a digital object (i.e., dataset, tool, system...) has machine-actionable features, then this can be exploited in a dynamic way by tools or services deployed on cloud computing resources. Those services can be integrated through different protocols to work together and compose workflows for data management [7]. For this automation procedures, metadata should describe the datasets in terms of context, content, physical details, etc. Taking this into consideration, metadata can be categorised in three different groups:

- **Descriptive metadata:** this set of features of datasets helps to make them findable. They describe a resource, its content, its identifying characteristics. This category includes unique or persistent identifiers and other attributes such as title, author, keywords, etc. This type of metadata uses Dublin Core as the main standard and referent. By making use of descriptive metadata, users can determine if the dataset is potentially useful.
- **Administrative metadata:** this set of metadata helps to make them accessible. Administrative metadata includes information about quality control, assurance and how the dataset has been created and any contextual information required to provide sustainable access to content. Specifically, the usually includes information about intellectual property rights (license type, embargo period, access rights details). Moreover, they usually have information about technical details (i.e., file format, file size, creation date and time, how to open, access and use it) and information about provenance, authenticity, preservation activity and technical environment.

- **Structural metadata:** This type of metadata helps to make digital objects interoperable and reusable. They describe how the pieces of a single object fit together and how an object exists in relationship to other objects. This includes information about its format or encoding and other logical details like the names of the variables, their units and the relationship with other objects or elements. Complex metadata standards like the Ecological Metadata Language, integrate different metadata elements at a structural level. They usually enable different mechanisms to automatise data management and harvesting.

Following Aguilar [7], “the exploitation of these three metadata levels following the common practices used in modern web applications and in cloud-based solutions can improve the scientific data quality and facilitate the access to a wider audience”. This information organised in the three groups enables the possibility of performing specific automatic actions on the data. Moreover, the use of these sets of features also helps to promote the FAIR principles [7].

5.1.4 EML - Ecological Metadata Language

The Ecological Metadata Language (EML [27, 28]) “defines a comprehensive vocabulary and a readable XML markup syntax for documenting research data” [28]. It was originally developed to describe digital objects within the ecology discipline. developed originally to describe digital objects, and specifically data, within the ecology discipline. It is modular and extensible, so different kinds of information are grouped in various categories, previously defined, that can be extended if it is needed. EML objectives are twofold: on one hand, defining a common structure for ecologists to completely describe their data and, therefore, data can be easily interpreted by other ecologists; on the other hand, EML provides a structure that allow software to automatically manage the data. This metadata standard supports the FAIR management of datasets and the implementation of basic tools, but also of complex applications that automatically integrate data. Therefore, it can be recommended to ecologists for handling long-term data complying with FAIR principles [7, 28]. In fact, it is used by relevant projects and infrastructures, like for example the Long Term Ecological Research Network (LTER).

The architecture of EML was defined to serve the needs of the research community and was designed based on previous work in other related metadata languages. Therefore, it can be compatible with other different implemented standards. Mainly, EML has been benefitted from Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, the Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata (CSDGM from the Federal Geographic Data Committee (FGDC)), the Biological Profile of the CSDGM (from the National Biological Information Infrastructure), the International Standards Organization’s Geographic Information Standard (ISO 19115), the ISO 8601 Date and Time Standard, the OpenGIS Consortiums’s Geography Markup Language (GML), the Scientific, Technical, and Medical Markup Language (STMML), and the Extensible Scientific Interchange Language (XSIL) [28]. The rules that govern the EML syntax is Extensible Markup Language (XML), that is an internet recommendation from the World Wide Web Consortium, and so a metadata document complies with the syntax of EML will structurally meet the criteria defined in the XML Schema documents for EML [28]. Besides the structure, XML schema allows for finer validation of the contents of the element. Therefore, when we validate an element, also the value that is inserted in the field of this element will be checked against the XML schema’s definition of this element. This makes EML very robust and reliable.

The modules defined in EML are containers that store a structured description of ecological (or agro-ecological) resources. The resource definition comes from the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, and the top-level structure of EML has been created to be compatible with the syntax provided by Dublin Core standards. These different modules are grouped into four levels:

- Root level: Base information of the resource, Dublin Core-like, including author, description, keywords and an identifier.
- Top-Level: Describes details from a different type of resources: datasets, software, protocols or literature.
- Supporting modules: This level qualifies the resources being described in more detail, like access rights, dimensional coverage, the methodology used to create the resource, etc.
- Data Organisation: Details the logical characteristics of the resource, like its internal structure, encoding, attributes, formats, types, etc.

The previous levels are complemented by other two categories: entity types, which include the information about the types used in the datasets, and utility models, that add secondary information in, for example, text form [28].

5.2 IDENTIFIERS

To uniquely recognise a resource such as a book, journal or any other research object, it must be properly identified. Since the 1970s, bibliographic identifiers such as ISBN and ISSN have been used to identify books and journals and this type of standardised code has made it possible to obtain information, metadata in fact, about the publication, such as title, edition, length, country, original language, etc. By using the ISBN code, a book can be uniquely referenced. In today's "digital age", many different types of research objects are available in digital form and can be exploited as a resource by the entire user community, as they can be easily accessed through the Internet. Therefore, a similar bibliographic format is needed to identify any digital resource. However, due to the digital context, the corresponding identifiers must satisfy various requirements. Traditional bibliographic mechanisms such as ISBNs are not actionable over the Internet, as they do not point directly to an accessible resource. Within the context of the World Wide Web and thanks to the use of the HTTP protocol, there **are different technical solutions to identify accessible resources**. The Uniform Resource Locator (URL) identifies the Internet address, using HTTP as the protocol of a resource, so that the object can be retrieved. The Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) identifies an abstract or physical resource, so it can be moved to another physical location without losing its identity (as a metaphor, the URI would be the ID number, which uniquely identifies it, and the URL would be its physical address).

To identify and retrieve a digital resource, both types of identifiers are required. Unlike a simple hyperlink, persistent identifiers are supposed to continue to provide access to a digital resource, even if it has been moved to another physical server or even to other organisations. A digital object can be moved, deleted or renamed for many reasons, but its identifier must remain accessible even if the resource is no longer accessible [7].

The first persistent identifier (PID) systems were launched shortly after the World Wide Web was launched in the mid-1990s to address the problem of non-persistent URLs. The Handle system was the first PID solution and was implemented in 1994. It is a distributed, general-purpose mechanism not only for identifying resources but also for resolving identifiers. It is composed of master and duplicate sites managed by the Corporation for National Research

Initiatives [7], and thanks to this distributed structure, the service guarantees availability and persistence.

Persistent URLs (PURLs) were proposed in 1995 as actionable identifiers, consisting of a URI pointing to a "resolver" that looks up the correct URL for the digital resource and returns it to the client via the HTTP protocol. The Uniform Resource Name (URN) was specified in 1997 and is a solution that requires the referenced resource to be available, but neither resolves nor resolves and lacks other features. Archival Resource Key (ARK), from 2001, is one of the most widespread solutions for PID. It was released by the US National Library of Medicine and its URL-based structure includes information within the identifier, such as the name of the hosting authority, the name or ID of the resource, and qualifiers. ARK is used to obtain three elements: the digital object itself, the metadata and the statement indicating the provider.

Although different solutions have existed for more than 20 years, there is no standard, not even "de facto" or a general agreement on its use. However, the **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)**, which was launched in 1998, is currently one of the most widespread and widely used solutions in the academic environment. The DOI is an indirect identifier of electronic documents based on Handle's "resolvers" and is a mechanism for the permanent identification of digital content, which first attempts to resolve the address of the resource and, if not available, returns the information or metadata attached to the identifier. Many journals and publishers now use the DOI as a bibliographic identifier, complementing other standards such as the ISBN. Currently, more than 130 million DOIs have been assigned by commercial and non-commercial providers participating in the International DOI Foundation [7]. The DOI format is composed of two sections: a numeric identifier that includes a prefix identifying the term as a DOI (10.) and a suffix identifying the publisher. The document is then identified with an additional code.

The DOI is a concrete implementation of the Handle system and, due to its extensibility and compatibility with other systems, is one of the most widespread. Since DOI and other persistent identification systems are available through HTTP-based web exploitation protocols, they are suitable for integration with service architecture systems. They are also very close to metadata, as they can integrate typical metadata values such as URL, authorship, email addresses, etc. On the other hand, they can be considered as one of the best options for identifiers within metadata standards.

5.3 REPOSITORIES AND CATALOGUES

Libraries, universities, governmental agencies or other research institutions can provide repositories to ensure scientific data respecting the FAIR principles will be available on the long term. Without this institutional support, the data life cycle will be limited to the experiment or project duration. Therefore, **scientific data repositories** will be an important aspect of interoperability, especially in the framework of EOSC, so protocols and communication mechanisms need to be enabled.

Today data users and data providers can easily access and contribute to resources and data online. The availability of data online is immense and associated to many heterogeneous sources. Our capacity to collect, store and manage data is supported by the progresses in computing power and storage capacity. Cloud computing services also plays a key role in supporting the management of repositories if they are supported using mechanisms that enable the exchange of information. An extra common layer among repositories is needed to maintain FAIRness because scientific data repositories are implemented independently, and they usually support many different data formats and have many accesses and ingest mechanisms. The Open Archive Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI PMH) can

help to data FAIRness while contributes to the compatibility of repositories. It provides technical support to FAIR principles implementation by developing interoperability standards to facilitate the dissemination of digital objects. Although initially the digital objects should be based on the Dublin Core standard, they can also be published using other metadata formats, as long as they are well defined. The aim of OAI PMH is to allow collecting metadata descriptions in a simple and standardized way and to define mechanisms for interconnecting different digital repositories.

One of the main challenge of data repositories is to provide a way for users to get access to the data and the services managing the data life cycle. In this regards, Authentication & Authorisation and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) is essential to manage the user access and should be a key element in data portals. SAML, OAuth, Open ID Connect are considered the main protocols to be integrated into AAAI solutions for a cloud environment and should be considered during the project implementation.

6. Conclusions

This deliverable aims to provide the **basis for the FAIR data management** that will be considered during ALL-Ready project implementation. **Data management** is essential for the entire data lifetime to avoid data loss, gain trust, improve reusability, increase transparency, improve data and research quality and increase efficiency. A key stage of data management is the planning phase. During that stage, data providers should identify data sources that will be used during the project, data and metadata formats that will be managed, instrumentation and computing resources that will be required, among other important topics (ethic and security issues, specific authorisations, specialised human resources needed, etc.). All these elements are included in a formal document, the Data Management Plan (DMP).

It is essential that data will follow the four **FAIR principles**: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The DMP will include information about how to maximise the FAIRness of data management. Becoming fully FAIR compliant presents many challenges for researchers and research data, mainly because the way to define the concept of FAIRness is continuously evolving. Standards and protocols for the description, interoperability, citation and reuse of data are central to FAIR principles. Metadata, persistent identifiers and storage solutions are among the tools that uphold FAIR principles.

Metadata provides information about the context and content of digital objects. This information guarantees data are findable and accessible to users and help to automation. Although a regular use of metadata in data management is missing, initiatives such as Research Data Alliance promotes best practices and technical solutions to build a sustainable system. Different standards have been identified, but Ecological Metadata Language (EML) can be considered as a candidate to be followed in agroecological works. The modules defined in EML are containers that store a structured description of ecological (or agro-ecological) resources. The resource definition comes from the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, and the top-level structure of EML has been created to be compatible with the syntax provided by Dublin Core standards.

Another essential aspect of data FAIRness is providing **persistent identifiers** to datasets. The DOI is a concrete implementation of the Handle system and, due to its extensibility and compatibility with other systems, is one of the most widespread. An interesting point of these identifiers is that they should return a description of the dataset and its context, although the dataset is temporally not accessible.

Finally, data preservation should also be addressed to secure long-term exploitation, taking into consideration security and legal matters, authorisation for access, licensing policies, etc. Scientific **data repositories** will be an important aspect of interoperability, especially in the framework of EOSC, so protocols and communication mechanisms need to be enabled. OAI PMH can help to data FAIRness while contributes to the compatibility of repositories. It provides technical support to FAIR principles implementation by developing interoperability standards to facilitate the dissemination of digital objects.

LifeWath ERIC is responsible for the preparation of the DMP for the ALL-Ready project. The DMP will contain information on the suggested policies, standards, and sustainability activities related to the created data services, including software solutions for the services. The research performed in this deliverable will be followed for the elaboration of the DMP of the project.

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